

Review

Drinking water contamination and its impact on human health

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Abstract: Water contamination is one of the important public health challenge in the world that humanity is facing in recently, access is to safe drinking water is essential for healthy life but waterborne disease is still a major cause of death in many parts of the world. The basis on which drinking water safety is judged is national standards or international guidelines. different substances are involve as water contaminants like inorganic, organic, bacterial and viral which constituent potential threat to water quality, chemical and microbial contaminants are responsible for various Human health problems. This review discusses detailed description of drinking water contaminants and human health effect in the consequent health problems, the data presented in this study are collected from various, national and international scientific journals.

Keywords: contaminants, Health effect, E. coli, infection

Introduction

Water is the most vital element among the natural resources, and is critical for the survival of all living organisms including human, food production, and economic development (Halder & Islam, 2015).

The global demand for safe drinking water is becoming increasingly important. The growing world population and anthropogenic activities cause the rapid contamination of water sources (Palansooriya et al., 2019).

The global demand for safe drinking water is becoming increasingly important. The growing world population and anthropogenic activities cause the rapid contamination of water sources. The

World Health Organization (WHO) reported that 2.1 billion people (equivalent to 29% of the global population) do not have access to safely managed drinking water (water free from contamination), and one out of three people does not use such water in rural areas (WHO & UNICEF, 2017).

An adequate supply of safe drinking water is one of the major prerequisites for a healthy life, but waterborne disease is still a major cause of death in many parts of the world, particularly in children, and it is also a significant economic constraint in many subsistence economies. Drinking water is derived from two basic sources: surface waters, such as rivers and reservoirs, and groundwater(John & Mark, 2003).

Many dangerous chemical elements if released into the environment, accumulate in the soil and sediments of water bodies(Mohod & Dhote, 2013).

The most challenging issue associated with surface water is the occurrence of organic, inorganic, and microbial contaminants, while exposure to these toxic substances can cause several health problems(Palansooriya et al., 2019).

The environment, economic growth, and developments are all highly influenced by water-its regional and seasonal availability, and the quality of surface and groundwater. The quality of water is affected by human activities and is declining due to the rise of urbanization, population growth, industrial production, climate change and other factors. The resulting water pollution is a serious threat to the well-being of both the Earth and its population(Halder & Islam, 2015).

The run-off or leaching of nutrients into slow flowing or still surface waters can result in excessive growth of cyanobacteria or blue-green algae¹. Many species give rise to nuisance chemicals that can cause taste and odour and interfere with drinking water treatment. However, they frequently produce toxins, which are of concern for health, particularly if there is only limited treatment. If treatment is not optimized, unwanted residues of chemicals used in water treatment can also cause contamination, and give rise to sediments in water pipes. Contamination during water distribution may arise from materials such as iron, which can corrode to release iron oxides, or from ingress of pollutants into the distribution system. Diffusion through plastic pipes can occur, for example when oil is spilt on the surrounding soil, giving rise to taste and odour problems. Contamination can also take place in consumers' premises from materials used in plumbing, such as lead or copper, or from the back-flow of liquids into the distribution system as a consequence

of improper connections. Such contaminants can be either chemical or microbiological(John & Mark, 2003).

The contamination of water resources has important repercussions for the environment and human health. Generally, drinking water containing different anions and heavy metals including metals, Cd, Cr, Co, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn and etc, has significant adverse effect on human health either through deficiency or toxicity due to excessive intake. Nitrate(NO_3) and nitrites(NO_2) are found naturally in water and the toxicology of nitrate to human is mainly attributable to its reduction to nitrite. The major biological effect of nitrite is its involvement in the oxidation of normal hemoglobin to methaemoglobin, which is unable to transport oxygen to tissue. The dominant human health risk associated with nitrate consumption is considered to be of methaemoglobinaemia by nitrate derived nitrite(khan et al., 2013).

The purpose of this review paper is to provide comprehensive understanding of drinking water contamination and its effects on the human health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted from several related text book, fresh sites of chemical institution and publication from highly valuable references. This writing surrounding more than 23 national and international scientific articles were taken as reference materials

Conclusion

Many substances are regarded as active water contaminants and are classified into different groups. The most common among them are pathogens (bacteria, viruses and protozoas), inorganic contaminants (acids, salts and toxic metals), anions and cations (nitrates, phosphate, sulphates, Ca^{+2} , Mg^{+2} and F^-) and water-soluble radioactive substances. In addition, organic compounds like oil and pesticides are also considered potential threats to water quality.(Azizullah,et al,2010). Besides the contaminants in water, esthetic water quality is also extremely important.(Palansooriya,et al,2019). All these substances, if they exceed a threshold value, are deleterious and cause severe health problems in humans and other organisms in the ecosystem.(Azizullah,et al,2010) The levels of contamination in drinking water depend on the type of water sources .(Palansooriya,*et al*,2019).

Inorganic contaminants: As indicated above, there are many chemical contaminants in drinking water. However, the most important contaminants from a health standpoint are naturally occurring chemicals that are usually found in groundwater. (Fawell & Nieuwenhuijsen,2020). The overall

situation of toxic metals in surface and groundwater shows a large variation in their contamination level and frequency. All toxic metals except copper and zinc have their concentrations beyond the critical limits in many cases. Most of the authors linked the elevated concentration of heavy metals in water to human activities like disposal of industrial, municipal and domestic wastes. (Wang & Zhuang,2018).

For inorganic contaminants, including heavy metals (e.g., Cr,Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, Pb, Hg,U, Pu) and metalloids (e.g., Se, As), the main challenge in assessing environmental risks is related to their contrasting behavior under different redox conditions. These elements are not subject to degradation like many of the organic pollutants the major processes that determine their transport and their bioavailability include oxidation/reduction, complexation, adsorption, and precipitation/dissolution reactions. Most metallic elements exhibit widely different solubility in the presence of oxygen and under reducing conditions. Under oxic conditions, the most abundant redox sensitive metals—iron and manganese—form finely dispersed oxide particles, which strongly adsorb heavy metals and metalloids.

When oxygen is depleted, these oxide particles undergo reductive dissolution and release their adsorbed toxic load.(Schwarzenbach *et al*,2010). as well as troublesome ions, including F⁻, NH₄⁺, PO₄³⁻, and NO₃⁻, are the common inorganic contaminants found in water bodies. Biochar can act as a dominant adsorbent for the removal of inorganic contaminants as it has shown very high degree of removal (up to 100%) depending on the status of the contaminant.(Palansooriya *et al*,2019). Heavy metals pose serious health threats even at very low concentrations. Some are cumulative poisons, capable of assimilation, storage and concentration by organisms exposed long periods to low concentrations. Eventual metal built-up in tissues can cause harmful physiological effects.(Mohan,2014). There are of course many other inorganic contaminants that can reach drinking water most of these are present in trace amounts, but some can be found in substantial quantities.(Harrison,2001). Zinc (Zn) and copper (Cu) are essential elements for human health but overexposure can lead to adverse health consequences for drinking water WHO set maximum acceptable concentrations of 3 mg/L and 2 mg/L for Zn and Cu, respectively. both these metals are usually found well below the WHO standard limits both in ground and surface water.(Azizullah *et al*,2010).

Selenium and uranium have also both been shown to cause adverse effects in humans through drinking water. In seleniferous areas, drinking water can contribute to high selenium intakes,

which can give rise to loss of hair, weakened nails and skin lesions, and more seriously, changes in peripheral nerves and decreased prothrombin time. Uranium is found in groundwater associated with granitic rocks and other mineral deposits. It is a kidney toxin and has been associated with an increase in fractional calcium excretion and increased microglobulinuria, although within the normal range found in the population. Uranium is a current topic of research with regard to exposure through drinking water. (Fawell & Nieuwenhuijsen, 2020). Manganese (Mn) is a naturally occurring mineral in surface and groundwater, but human activities also contribute much to its introduction in water. (Azizullah *et al*, 2010).

Arsenic occurs in drinking water primarily as a consequence of dissolution from arsenic bearing rocks into groundwater. Although problems in the UK are very limited, arsenic is a major problem in many parts of the world including the Indian sub-continent, South America, the far east and the United States. Iron can occur at high concentrations in some source waters that are anaerobic. When the water is aerated they are oxidized to oxides that are of low solubility. These will cause significant discolouration and turbidity at concentrations well below those of any concern for health. They may, however, cause consumers to turn to alternative supplies which may be more aesthetically acceptable but which are microbiologically unsafe. (Fawell & Nieuwenhuijsen, 2020). Mercury (Hg) is a naturally occurring element and a “persistent bioaccumulative toxin. It is introduced to the environment through various natural processes as well as different human activities. According to the WHO standards, its concentration in drinking water should not exceed 0.001 mg/L. (Azizullah *et al*, 2010). Nickel, dubbed as “Allergen of the Year 2008”, is a widely distributed element in the environment, and can be found in air, water and soil. (Schwarzenbach *et al* 2010).

Waterborne fluoride is another major cause of morbidity in a number of parts of the world, including the Indian sub-continent, Africa and the Far East, where concentrations of fluoride can exceed 10 mg/l. High intakes of fluoride can give rise to dental fluorosis, an unsightly brown mottling of teeth, but higher intakes result in skeletal fluorosis, a condition arising from increasing bone density and which can eventually lead to fractures and crippling skeletal deformity. A WHO working group concluded that skeletal fluorosis and an increased risk of bone fractures occur at a total intake of 14 mg fluoride per day, and there is evidence suggestive of an increased risk of bone effects at intakes above about 6 mg fluoride per day. This is a major cause of morbidity and can manifest itself at a relatively early age with the result that affected individuals cannot work

properly and may be economically as well as physically disadvantaged for life. Many factors appear to influence the risk of such adverse effects, including volume of drinking water, nutritional status and, particularly, fluoride intake from other sources.(Fawell & Nieuwenhuijsen,2020).

Nitrate is found in both surface and groundwater sources for drinking water, primarily as a consequence of agricultural activity. This is not simply due to the use of excessive amounts of artificial fertilizers but the presence of excess nitrate from any source when there is insufficient plant growth to take up that excess and when rainfall is present to cause leaching from the soil. Indeed one of the major sources of nitrate in some groundwaters was the ploughing of ancient grassland following the Second World War. While the appearance of nitrate in surface water following a leaching event can be quite rapid, it may take many years for nitrate to reach some groundwaters, which can mean that that, even when surface inputs stop, the levels in groundwater will continue to rise for some time after. In some cases this can be more than 10 years.(Harrison,2001).

Organic contaminants: There are many organic substances that can reach drinking water sources, either as a consequence of discharges of wastewater or run-off from urban and agricultural areas." Most are present in extremely small concentrations of no more than a few microgrammes per litre but occasionally much higher concentrations can be encountered as a consequence of spills.Organic contaminants are found in the greatest number in surface water but some can, and do, reach groundwater.(Harrison,2001). Most organic substances are potential pollutants as they enter groundwater or surface water, since they may cause a depletion of dissolved oxygen . However, some organic compounds are directly toxic, thereby potentially causing direct harmful effects on living organisms and ecosystems. These organic compounds include petroleum and its derivatives, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and chlorinated hydrocarbons.(Perk,2006). Contamination of water resources in catchment areas of agricultural land and continuous exposure of humans and biota to biologically active chemicals are of great concern. Peak concentrations of pesticides and their transformation products, such as the frequently detected triazines or chloroacetanilides in U.S. rivers can exceed ecotoxic levels for nontarget organisms in soils and aquatic systems and compromise the use of surface and groundwater for drinking water supplies.(Schwarzenbach *et al*,2010).

Most polluting organic compounds are man-made and industrially produced, although a number of these chemicals also occur naturally, produced by biochemical synthesis, incomplete

decomposition of organic matter, volcanic eruptions, forest fires, or lightning.(wang,1994). In the last four decades, the use of pesticides has increased substantially throughout the world. It aims at protection of crops from insect infestation to achieve higher crop yields with better quality an estimated quantity of 2.5 million tons of pesticides is used in the world annually with continuous increases .(Mohan,2014). One of the most common groups of contaminants cited by the media, and various pressure groups, as a problem in drinking water is pesticides.(Aziziullah,*et al* ,2010). problems arise with Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) in drinking water the cause is usually the disturbance of sediment in water mains and is, therefore, a consequence of particulate matter. In these circumstances the water would be discoloured and, possibly, would also give rise to taste and odour problems. The problem can be rapidly identified and exposure through drinking water can be minimized.(Harrison,2001).

Tri- and tetrachloroethene.. These two substances which were widely used as chlorinated solvents have caused significant problems in some groundwaters. They are not found at significant concentrations in surface waters because they are rapidly lost to the atmosphere. However, they are poorly adsorbed to soil and are only degraded extremely slowly so when spilt on the ground they can move down to groundwater where they are very persistent.(Schwarzenbach *et al*,2010). Petroleum or crude oil consists of a complex mixture of many different chemical compounds ranging from very volatile, light compounds like pentane and benzene , to heavy compounds such as bitumens and asphaltenes. It contains mainly hydrocarbons (i.e. organic compounds made up of only carbon and hydrogen) of the alkane series, which usually make up about 95 percent of the crude oil. These aliphatic components are barely soluble in water. Crude oil also includes impurities such as monocyclic and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons . The remaining part is comprised of small amounts of oxygen , nitrogen , and sulphur, and traces of other elements, such as heavy metals.(post *et al*,2012). Environmental pollution by petroleum and oil products may occur during extraction, refinement, transport, storage, and use. Spills and leaks are the principal causes of oil pollution of soil, groundwater, and surface water.(Perk,2006).

Microbial contamination: The contamination of drinking water by pathogens causing diarrhoeal disease is the most important aspect of drinking water quality. The problem arises as a consequence of contamination of water by faecal matter, particularly human faecal matter, containing pathogenic organisms.(Fawell & Nieuwenhuijsen,2020). For pathogenic microorganisms, besides

the cell or organism itself, there are many levels of morphological components that can sometimes be used to identify pathogens.(Gersten & Sonderby,2009).

One of the great scourges of cities in Europe and North America in the 19th century was outbreaks of waterborne diseases such as cholera and typhoid. In many parts of the developing world it remains a major cause of disease. It is therefore essential to break the faecal–oral cycle by preventing faecal matter from entering water sources and/or by treating drinking water to kill the pathogens.(Calabrese *et al*,2006). detection and enumeration of pathogens in water are not appropriate under most circumstances in view of the difficulties and resources required so *Escherichia coli* and faecal streptococci are used as indicators of faecal contamination.(Fawell & Nieuwenhuijsen,2020). The assumption is that if the indicators are detected, pathogens, including viruses, could also be present and therefore appropriate action is required. However, the time taken to carry out the analysis means that if contamination is detected, the contaminated water will be well on the way to the consumer and probably drunk by the time the result has been obtained.(Azizullah *et al*,2010). In addition the small volume of water sampled (typically 100 ml) means that such check monitoring on its own is not an adequate means of assuring drinking water safety.(Vigil,2003). it is also essential to ensure that the multiple barriers are not only in place but working efficiently at all times, whatever the size of the supply.(Mohan,2014).

Drinking water is not, however, sterile and bacteria can be found in the distribution system and at the tap.(Post *et al*,2012). most of these organisms are harmless, but some opportunist pathogens such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Aeromonas* spp. may multiply during distribution given suitable conditions.Currently there is some debate as to whether these organisms are responsible for any waterborne, gastrointestinal disease in the community but *P. aeruginosa* is known to cause infections in immunocompromised patients and weakened patients in hospitals.((Fawell & Nieuwenhuijsen,2020). microbial contamination of drinking water thus remains a significant threat and constant vigilance is essential, even in the most developed countries.(Perk,2006).

Source of contaminants: Water can be contaminated from both natural and anthropogenic sources. All surface waters will contain natural organic matter in the form of humic substances, large complex carbohydrate molecules. Some will contain inorganic substances dissolved from the minerals through which the water percolates and some will contain particles of clay and sand washed from the surrounding catchment, the banks and the bottom sediments.(Harrison,2001).Drinking water is derived from two basic sources, surface waters, such

as rivers and reservoirs, and groundwater. All water contains natural contaminants, particularly inorganic contaminants that arise from the geological strata through which the water flows and, to a varying extent, anthropogenic pollution by both microorganisms and chemicals. In general, groundwater is less vulnerable to pollution than surface waters.(Fawell & Nieuwenhuijsen,2020). Groundwater contamination can be classified as having either natural or anthropogenic sources.(Alper & Tayfur,2010). There are a number of possible sources of man made contaminants, some of which are more important than others. These fall into the categories of point and diffuse sources. Discharges from industrial premises and sewage treatment works are point sources and as such are more readily identifiable and controlled, in the UK.(Pye & Patrick,2105). The major industries contributing to water pollution are textile, pharmaceuticals, ceramics, petrochemicals, food industries, steel, oil mills, sugar industries, fertilizer factories, and leather tanning These industries produce several hundred thousands of wastewater containing huge quantities of pollutants.

Contamination can also take place in consumer's premises from materials used in plumbing or from back siphoning of liquids into the distribution system as a consequence of improper connections, in breach of by-laws. Such contaminants can be either chemical or microbiological.(Palansoorya *et al* ,2019). Contaminants may be present most of the time, in which case the issue for consumers is chronic exposure and chronic toxicity, or for short periods, such as in a spill penetrating treatment, in which case the issue is likely to be acute toxicity following short-term exposure.(Alper & Tayfur,2011).

Impacts of water contamination on human health: According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), water contamination water contamination can affect nearly every system in the body. water is used not only for drinking but also for "handwashing, bathing, and recreational uses, not to mention the way it's used in industry and agriculture. It must therefore "be safe and clean and free from disease-causing organisms (Brass, 1982). Some of the harmful effects of water pollution on human health include.

Acute and Chronic Health Effects: Toxic doses of chemicals cause either acute or chronic health effects. An acute effect usually follows a large dose of a chemical and occurs almost immediately. Examples of acute health effects are nausea, lung irritation, skin rash, vomiting, dizziness and even death. The levels of chemicals in drinking water, however, are seldom high enough to cause acute health effects. They are more likely to cause chronic health effects. effects that occur long after exposure to small amounts of a chemical. Examples of chronic health effects include; cancer, birth

defects, organ damage, disorders of the nervous system, and damage to the immune system(ELAINE & JACK, 2016).

Bacterial infections Cholera: It is a bacterial disease. Polluted water is generally the medium to spread this disease. *Vibrio cholera* is the one who is responsible for causing this disease. Cholera leads to thousands of deaths every year due to the consumption of polluted water. This bacterium generates toxins in the digestive tracts of the infected person. As far as cholera symptoms are concerned, the infected person usually gets very mild or no symptoms at all. However, about one in ten infected persons may experience the symptoms of cholera such as vomiting, leg cramps, and profuse watery diarrhea.

Salmonella: Salmonella is a kind of bacteria. It may cause infection when ingested within the human body through polluted water. Salmonellosis infects the intestinal tracts of a person who consumes contaminated water, having this bacterium. An infected person may have symptoms of Salmonella fever, diarrhoea, abdominal cramps, headaches, and in some cases, vomiting & loss of appetite.(Wu, C & et al., 1099).

E.Coli: *Escherichia Coli* is a common bacteria found in the intestines of a healthy person. However, the E. Coli bacteria are also associated with some harmful strains that may cause severe implications if consumed. These symptoms mostly include abdominal cramps, vomiting, diarrhoea, etc.

Botulism: It is a sporadic type of poisoning caused by a toxin named *Clostridium botulism*. The bacteria may cause paralysis in the infected person that starts from the face and then spreads to the limbs. In some cases, the situation may be critical if it allows the spread and paralyzes the muscles used for breathing. In this case, the condition may lead to respiratory failure.

Typhoid: Typhoid is a fever mainly caused by consuming contaminated food or water. It is an acute illness related to fever caused by a bacterium known as *Salmonella enterica* serotype Typhi. The infected person may get these symptoms of typhoid- high fever, weakness, headache, stomach-ache, loss of appetite, etc.

Dysentery: Dysentery is a disease caused by water pollution. It is inflammation of the intestines & usually leads to bloody diarrhoea. In general, dysentery is caused by a bacterium known as *Shigella*. However, dysentery is also caused by some other kinds of viruses, protozoa, or parasite found in water(Rhoda, G & et al., 1994).

Hepatitis E: It is also a kind of infectious liver disease caused by a virus known as hepatitis E. This disease is mostly related to the countries that have poor sanitation practices. People who got hepatitis E infection may suffer from fatigue, jaundice, vomiting, joint pain, fever, nausea, etc.

Chemical contamination and health: Chemical contamination of drinking-water may also have effects on health, although in general these tend to be chronic rather than acute, unless a specific pollution event has occurred and are therefore generally considered of lower priority than microbiological contamination.

Chemical pollutants which affect health include lead, nitrate, arsenic, mercury and fluoride. In addition, there are an ever-increasing number of synthetic organic compounds released into the environment whose effect on human health is poorly understood, but which it appears may be carcinogenic(Vodela, J et al., 1997).

Lead: Lead-filled water affects everyone exposed to it, but the effects are exacerbated in children, the elderly, and pregnant women. the effects of lead in children can include behavioral and attention-related issues, delayed puberty, impaired hearing, stunted growth, and decreased cognitive ability, IQ, and academic achievement. In adults, health effects can include hypertension, nerve disorders including tremors and other disorders of the central nervous system, decreased kidney function, and fertility problems(Mohan, D & et al., 2014).

Nitrate: Excess nitrate in drinking-water has been linked to methaemoglobinemia in infants, the so-called 'blue-baby' syndrome. Nitrate leads to the oxidation of normal haemoglobin to methaemoglobin which is unable to transport oxygen to the tissues. This may result in cyanosis (a dark blue coloration) and in some cases, asphyxiation and death.

Arsenic: In some parts of the world, natural sources of arsenic may contaminate water supplies and lead to poisoning of the users. The most well-documented cases of arsenic poisoning from drinking-water have come from India, where there is arsenic contamination of large numbers of rural water supplies. Common symptoms include inflamed eyes and skin lesions(Vodela, J et al., 1997).

Fluoride: Fluoride in drinking-water can have toxic effects in both excess and deficiency, although WHO only set a GV of 1.5 mg/l for excess fluoride as susceptibility in deficiency is highly dependent on nutritional status. Excess fluoride may lead to dental or skeletal fluorosis, the latter being a crippling disease which affects a number of areas including the Rift valley of East Africa and parts of India, Mexico and the former Soviet Union. (ATSDR, 2015).

Result

Many substances are regarded as active water contaminants and are classified into different groups. The most common among them are pathogens (bacteria, viruses and protozoas), inorganic contaminants (acids, salts and toxic metals), anions and cations and water-soluble radioactive substances. In addition, organic compounds like oil and pesticides are also considered potential threats to water quality. The levels of contamination in drinking water depend on the type of water sources. Most metallic elements exhibit widely different solubility in the presence of oxygen and under reducing conditions. Heavy metals pose serious health threats even at very low concentrations. Some are cumulative poisons. Organic contaminants are found in the greatest number in surface water but some can, and do, reach groundwater. Most organic substances are potential pollutants as they enter groundwater or surface water, since they may cause a depletion of dissolved oxygen. contamination of drinking water by pathogens causing diarrhoeal disease is the most important aspect of drinking water quality. The assumption is that if the indicators are detected, pathogens, including viruses, could also be present and therefore appropriate action is required.

Enteric diseases spread mostly via water contaminated with feces from ill persons and animals. Hence, assessing treatment schemes, including the potential for water recycling, with regard to the transfer of waterborne pathogens, requires reliable hygienic drinking water quality parameters. In addition, the general microbiological state of water is assessed by counting the total number of colony-forming microbes growing on a nutrient agar plate. As a consequence, it is becoming current practice to rely exclusively on the presence/absence of *E. coli* to judge the hygienic quality of drinking water. However, this approach is not suited for monitoring the hygienic quality of water treatment and distribution. Although the detection of *E. coli* will remain the hygiene parameter for the next decades. Increasing water temperatures as well as severe rainfall and flooding events as a consequence of climate change are likely to impact the spreading patterns and frequency of infectious disease outbreaks. contaminated water can be causes deferent infectious diseases, such as dengue, West Nile fever, yellow fever, and malaria.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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